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(ii) *Chapter in a book* : Ingle JI, Simon JH, Mahtou P. Outcome of endodontic treatment and re-treatment. In: Ingle JI, Bakland LK, editors. *Endodontics*, 5th ed. Ontario: BC Decker, 2002: P. 747-765.

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CONTENTS

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

- Caries and Associated Factors among Pre-school Children: A Descriptive Study** 01
MAI Khan, NH Sajib, S Parvin
- Detection Of Antinuclear Antibodies: Comparative Evaluation Of Enzyme Immunoassay And Indirect Immunofluorescence Methods** 04
T Begum, AKM S Moral, AFMS Rahman, MM Hasan
- Health Education Intervention on Hand Washing in a selected Primary School Children** 07
MSA Farzan, I Zerin, MA Kabir, MSR Pavel, MS Hossain

REVIEW ARTICLE

- Review on Dental implants Success and Failures** 12
MM Hasan
- Childhood Obesity: A Challenge for Pediatric Dentistry** 14
G Mohammad, MM Rahman, F Jerin

CASE REPORT

- Orthodontic treatment of Skeletal Class II division 1 malocclusion : A case report** 18
MW Ali, MZ Hossain
- Dental Technique Improve Smile and Confidence “A Case Report of Post-Traumatic Discolored Teeth-30 Month Follow Up”** 23
SS Beauty, AA Moral, MS Alam
- Pattern and Distribution of Jaw fracture: A study conducted on 422 patients of jaw fracture** 25
AFMS Rahman, T Begum, M Hasan, M Ahmed

Caries and Associated Factors among Pre-school Children: A Descriptive Study

MAI Khan¹, NH Sajib², S Parvin³

Abstract:

This descriptive cross-sectional study on oral health status of Pre-school children between two to five years of age was carried out among 107 children attending the Outpatient Department of Sapporo Dental College and Hospital, situated at Uttara, Dhaka. The objective of the study was to assess the oral health status of children upto five years of age through decayed, missing and filled teeth (dmft) status of their primary teeth and to find out the tooth cleaning habits and food habits of the study children. Data was collected both in English and Bengali with a pretested structured questionnaire and a checklist. On analysis of data dental caries (d) was found in 69.2% of the children, while missing (m) and filled (f) teeth were recorded in 14% and 21.5% of the children respectively. In all 72% of the children demonstrated an overall dmft score 1 or higher; whereas 28% of the children demonstrated dmft score 0 or were free from any form of dental decay, missing teeth or dental filling. The number of decayed, missing or filled teeth increased with increasing age of the children and this finding was statistically highly significant ($P < 0.01$). Male children showed higher prevalence of dental caries compared to the female children. Daily teeth cleaning were practiced by 95% of the children. Tooth brush and toothpaste was used by 83.2% and 84.1% of the children respectively. The study revealed that an acceptable method of brushing was practiced by only 44% of the children and brushing for the recommended 1-3 minutes was done by 37.3% only. Children who had their parents brush their teeth had less carious experience compared to the children who brushed their teeth by themselves and this finding was statistically significant ($P < .05$).

Introduction.

The oral health of preschool children (2-5 years of age) remains a neglected area of health as ever Data related to prevalence of caries specifically of deciduous teeth, are rare in our country. Although studies regarding older children and adults are not available, the importance of doing systematic research on preschool children has been overlooked. In the developed countries, measures taken through research findings have reduced the incidence of dental diseases in preschool children to manifold from the decade before, at the same time caries of primary teeth increased in developing countries^{3,4,8,9}.

In Bangladesh the extent and magnitude of dental caries among children with primary dentition have not been

extensively explored. The World Health Organization (WHO) also does not have any data base on the oral health status of under-five children in Bangladesh².

This study was conducted among two to five years age children with the consent of their parents at the outpatient department (OPD) of Sapporo Dental College and Hospital, Uttara, Dhaka. The primary objective of this study was to find out the caries status and associated factors in under-five children in order to help develop preventive dental care approaches.

Materials and Methods

This descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out at the Outpatient Department of Sapporo Dental College and Hospital, Uttara, Dhaka. One hundred and seven children between two to five years of age and having only primary teeth were selected by convenient sampling technique. A pretested structured questionnaire and a checklist for clinical examination were used for data collection. The children and their parents were respondents of the questionnaire. Data was collected by the researcher and trained OPD dental surgeons. Face-to-face interview of parent/ children and dental examination of the children were carried out after verbal consent of the guardians.

The decayed, missing, filled teeth (dmft) component of oral health was recorded during the clinical examination. Materials used for clinical examination were-dental probes, dental mirrors, cotton and antiseptic

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solution. The children were seated on a dental chair and dental examination was carried out under direct light with mirror and caries probe. Carious teeth (d), the missing (m) and filled teeth (f) were also counted. Data analysis was done using SPSS 11.5 for Windows version according to the key variable and objectives of the study.

Results

Table 1: Distribution of children according to carious teeth and sex of the child

N=107

Sex of the child	Carious or decayed teeth		Total No. 100%
	YES	NO	
	No. %	No. %	
Male	37 75.5%	12 24.5%	49 100.0%
Female	37 63.8%	21 36.2%	58 100.0%
Total	74 69.2%	33 30.8%	107 100.0%

Table 1 shows that among the participating 107 children, 49 were male and 58 were female children. Male children under five years of age had a higher prevalence of caries (75.5%) compared to female children (63.8%) of the same age.

Table 2: Distribution of the children according to age of the children and dmft score

N=107

Age in years	dmft score		
	dmft score 0	dmft 1 or higher	Total
	No. %	No. %	No. %
2-3 years	17 56.7%	9 24.3%	26 66.7%
3-4 years	7 23.3%	21 26.2%	28 68.3%
4-5 years	6 20.0%	47 49.5%	53 63.0%
Total	30 100%	77 100%	107 100%

P=.000(<.01)

Table 2 shows that dmft score of 1 or higher increases with the increasing age of the children. There exists significant relation between age of children and dmft scores (P=.000, <.01).

Table 3: Distribution of the children by assisted tooth cleaning and dmft score

N=107

Characteristic	dmft score		
	dmft score 0	dmft 1 or higher	Total
	No. %	No. %	No. %
Child cleans own teeth	18 60%	64 83.1%	82 100%
Assisted tooth cleaning	12 40%	13 16.9%	25 100%
Total	30 100%	77 100%	107 100%

P= .01 (<.05)

Table 3 shows caries state was higher (83.1%) in children who brush their own teeth as compared to those children who enjoy assistance from their parents (16.9%).

Table 4: Distribution of children according to snacking and tooth cleaning habits

N=107

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Snacking habit between meals		
Yes	106	99.1%
No	1	0.9%
Tooth cleaning after snacking		
Yes	3	2.8%
No	103	97.2%

Table 4 shows snacking after meal was observed in 99.1% of the participants but only 2.8% of children cleaned their teeth after a snack food.

Table 5: Distribution of the children according to regularity, frequency, method, timing and time taken for tooth cleaning.

N=107

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Daily tooth cleaning		
Regular	102	95.3%
Irregular	5	4.7%
Frequency of cleaning		
Once daily	71	69.6%
Twice daily	31	30.4%
Method of brushing		
Correct method	47	44%
Others	60	56%
Proper timing of brushing		
Yes	9	8.4%
No	98	91.6%
Time taken for brushing		
1-3 mins	40	37.3%
Others	67	62.7%

Discussion and Conclusion

The study findings revealed 69.2% of the under-five children had carious deciduous teeth, which is similar to findings of some developing countries^{8,9,10,11}. It was observed that prevalence of caries increased with increase in the age of children, $P < .01$ (Table 2), indicating caries begins at very young age, and its incidence will continue to rise with age without early measures for prevention. This result was quite similar with some earlier findings in Bangladesh¹³ which reported an increase in caries prevalence with increasing age.

The study also revealed that assisted brushing by parents at this age group could be an important factor in lowering caries incidence (table 3) as such young children fail to clean their teeth in ideal manner (table 5).

If snacking habit of children were to be taken into consideration (table 4), the importance of cleaning or at least rinsing after snack is to be emphasized to the children and their parents.

The results of this study definitely indicate negligence and lack of awareness for taking care of children teeth

among the parents attending the OPD. Educating both children and their parents about oral health should be made an integral part of health care delivery system.

References

1. Reich E, Lussi A, Newburn E. Caries risk assessment. *International Dental Journal*. 1999; 49:15-26.
2. WHO Oral Health Country/Area Profile Programme. Source: <http://www.whocollab.od.mah.se/index.htm>
3. Andlaw RJ and Rock WP. *Manual of Paediatric Dentistry*, 4th Edition, USA: Churchill Livingstone, 1996; 132.
4. Rao A. *Principles and Practice of Pedodontics*. 1st Edition. New Delhi: Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers, 2006; 138.
5. Douglass JM, Douglass HJ, Silk HJ. A practical guide to infant oral health. *American Family Physician*. 2004; 70:2113-2120.
6. Midda M and Konig KG. Nutrition, diet and oral health. *International Dental Journal*. 1994; 44:599-612.
7. Nunn JH. The burden of oral ill health. *Archives of Diseases in Childhood*. 2006; 91:251-253.
8. Mohebbi SZ, Virtanen JI, Mojtaba VG, Vehkalahat MM. Early childhood caries and dental plaque among 1-3-year olds in Teheran, Iran. *Journal of Indian Society of Pedodontics and Preventive Dentistry*. 2006; 24(4):177-181
9. Mahejabeen R, Sudha P, Kulkarni SS, Anegundi R. Dental caries prevalence among preschool children of Hubli: Dharwad city. *Journal of Indian Society of Pedodontics and Preventive Dentistry*. 2006; 24(1):19-22.
10. Sayegh A, Dini EL, Holt RD, Bedi R. Food and drink consumption, sociodemographic factors and dental caries in 4-5-year-old children in Amman, Jordan. *British Dental Journal* 2002; 193 (1): 37-42.
11. Necmi N, Vehit HE, Can G. Risk factors for dental caries in Turkish preschool children. *Journal of Indian Society of Pedodontics and Preventive Dentistry*. 2005; 23(3):115-118.
12. Brown LJ. Dental caries and sealant usage in US children 1988-1991. *Journal of American Dental Association*. 1996; 127:335-343.
13. Haque MJ and Begum JA. Dental caries – a persisting problem in the pre-school age children. *Journal of Preventive and social medicine*. 1994; 13(2-4): 98-101.
14. Rahim MA, Sikder MNH, Kabir MH, Abdullah US. Studies on the DMF level among sugar in taking children. *Bangladesh Dental Journal*. 1996; 12(1):48-51.
15. Bhuiyan AM. Prevalence of dental diseases in Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Dental Journal*. 1988-89; 5(1): 6-9.

Detection Of Antinuclear Antibodies: Comparative Evaluation Of Enzyme Immunoassay And Indirect Immunofluorescence Methods

T Begum¹, AKM S Moral², AFMS Rahman³, MM Hasan⁴

Abstract:

The suspicion of autoimmune disease primarily starts with clinical symptoms. Serological tests for Antinuclear Antibodies (ANA) an important role towards the diagnosis of various autoimmune diseases. Objective-To compare ELISA and IIF on HEp-2 cell methods for detecting ANA. A total 122 serum sample obtained from patients with established on suspected autoimmune diseases and 61 sample for ANA test, 24 for anti dsDNA test and 37 for antiCCP test using both IIF and ELISA methods. Sensitivity of ANA was found to be 73 % and specificity was found to be 47%. Based on the results ANA is found to detect 73% of the immune-fluorescence test positive cases correctly and able to detect 47% of the immune-fluorescence test negative cases correctly. Specificity of ANA in the current study is found to be quite low, although sensitivity is optimum.

Sensitivity of Anti CCP was found to be 39 % and specificity was found to be 64%. Based on the results Anti CCP is found to detect 39% of the immune-fluorescence test positive cases correctly and able to detect 64% of the immune-fluorescence test negative cases correctly.

It was concluded that IIF on HEp-2 cell is more sensitive than ELISA in detecting the total ANA . ELISA prescreening combined with IIF can obtained the information of the nuclear pattern and allow the observation. The combination of two testing methods can greatly enhance the accuracy of the results.

Key words: Discolored broken matured permanent teeth, non-vitality, apical, radiolucency, full veneer crown.

Introduction

The measurement of autoantibodies against antigens of the nucleus (antinuclear antibodies (ANA) is commonly used for screening, diagnosis, and monitoring of connective tissue diseases (CTD) such as systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE), progressive systemic sclerosis (PSS), mixed connective tissue disease (MCTD), Sjogren syndrome (SS), and polymyositis (PM). The preferred technique is indirect immunofluorescence

(IIF) on HEp-2, a human epithelial cell line, as an antigen source ^{1,2}

More recently, enzyme immunoassays (EIA) have been introduced for the detection and measurement of ANA. They differ mainly by the antigen composition used in each well: while screening tests use whole HEp-2 nuclei, an extract thereof, or a mixture of defined nuclear antigens, diagnostic tests use a single defined antigen, allowing the qualitative assessment of four to six different antibodies, i.e., an antibody profile, in one run ³.

Compared to IIF, the EIA technique is objective, is less labor-intensive, and has the potential for automation. At the same time, however, it is more expensive. It provides results in optical densities (ODs) rather than titers and gives the antibody specificity rather than the ANA pattern, i.e., it has an impact both on the logistics of clinical laboratories performing the ANA test and on the thinking of the clinician ordering it. No doubt, this technique has been put on the market in the hope that it will supplement the existing IIF technique or even replace it⁴.

Our study is, based on a fairly large number of consecutively collected, clinically defined sera, and the

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data were obtained at a routine laboratory. In addition, we provide an extensive validation of the IIF on HEp-2 cell technique as such, with one of the laboratories comparing HEp-2 and against an ANA screen EIA⁵.

Materials and Methods:

This experimental study was conducted on a total 122 subjects. Laboratory works were carried out in the Department of Microbiology & Immunology, Rheumatology Center and SLE clinic of Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University, Dhaka, Bangladesh in the period of July 2008 to June 2009.

All subjects were interviewed and findings recorded on a pre designed data sheet irrespective of age and sex . Out of 122 patients - 61 patients for ANA test, 24 patients for Anti ds DNA test and 37 patients for Anti CCP test Sample collection and storage

Approximately 5 ml blood samples was collected by venepuncture and sera was separated as soon as possible, aliquoted and stored at -20 ° C, repeated thawing and freezing was avoided.

Laboratory method by-

- A) Detection of antinuclear antibody by indirect immunofluorescence method on HEp-2 cell line .
- B) Detection of Antinuclear Antibodies (ANA) by ELISA method .
- C) Detection of Anti ds DNA by ELISA method.
- D) Detection of Anti CCP by ELISA method.

Result

Figure 1: Distribution of the study population by age cases (n = 122)

Figure 1 shows the distribution of the respondents among the study participants highest percentage were in between 20-29 years age group that was 32%.

Figure 2: Distribution of the study population by Sex (n=122)

Pie chart shows the distribution of the study participants by sex. Among the participants 21.3% were male and 78.7% were female.

Table 1: Results of ELISA done for Anti CCP, Anti dsDNA and ANA test in study population(n=122)

Table 1.1 ELISA done for ANA of study groups (n=61)

ANA	Frequency	Percent
ANA+ve	38	62.3
ANA-ve	23	37.7
Total	61	100.0

Antinuclear Test for anti nuclear antibody test was done in 61 patients among them 62.3% were found to be positive (ANA +ve) and 37.7% were found to be negative (ANA).

Table 1.2: ELISA done for AntidsDNA of study groups (n=24)

AntidsDNA	Frequency	Percent
AntidsDNA+ve	15	62.5
AntidsDNA-ve	9	37.5
Total	24	100.0

AntidsDNA Frequency Percent AntidsDNA+ve 15 62.5 AntidsDNA-ve 9 37.5 Total 24 100.0

Test AntidsDNA was done in 24 patients among them 62.5% were found to be positive (Anti dsDNA +ve) and 37.5% were found to be negative (Anti dsDNA -ve).

Table 1.3: ELISA-Anti CCP done in study group (n=37).

ELISA	Frequency	Percent
Anti CCP + ve	14	37.8
Anti CCP - ve	23	62.2
Total	37	100

ELISA test was done in 37 patients, among them 37.8% were found to be Anti CCP positive + ve and 62.2% were found to be Anti CCP – ve.

Figure 3: Accuracy of ANA in comparison to Immunofluorescence in terms of sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and Accuracy

Diagnostic preciseness of ANA results were assessed based on immunofluorescence test. Sensitivity of ANA was found to be 73 % and specificity was found to be 47%. Based on the results ANA is found to detect 73% of the immune-fluorescence test positive cases correctly and able to detect 47% of the immune-fluorescence test negative cases correctly. Specificity of ANA in the current study is found to be quite low,

Discussion

Test for antinuclear antibody (ANA) in serum is now an accepted part of routine diagnostic evaluation in patients with connective tissue disease. Detection of ANA by indirect immunofluorescence(IIF) method is highly sensitive for CTD. In this study we calculated both of these performance characteristics for a commercial ELISA & IIF method for ANA. The result presented in this study shows that maximum CTD patients were in 20-29 years of age group followed by 30- 39 years group and among CTD patients 21.3% were male and 78.7% were female.

Several studies revealed that CTD condition was the increased susceptibility of the female sex. Women are at least tenfold more likely to develop SLE ⁶.

In this study, ELISA and IIF -test were done in 122 patients. Among them ANA done in 61 patients , AntidsDNA done in 24 patients and Anti-CCP test was done in 37 patients.

Antinuclear antibody test done by ELISA in 61 patients, among them 62.3% were found to be positive ANA and 37.7% were found to be negative ANA.

Test Anti dsDNA was done by ELISA in 24 patients, among them 62.5% were found to be positive AntidsDNA and 37.5% were found to be negative Anti dsDNA.

Among 37 patients of Anti-CCP, 37.8% were found to be Anti CCP positive and 62.2% were found to be Anti CCP negative. ANA has been reported positive and in high titres in almost all cases of SLE ^{7,8,9,10,11,12}.

Immuno-fluorescence test was done in 122 subjects. The test is considered as gold standard test to assess the accuracy of

,ANA Anti dsDNA and Anti-CCP test. Diagnostic preciseness of ANA results were assessed based on immunofluorescence test. Sensitivity of ANA was found to be 73 % and specificity was found to be 47%. Based on the results ANA is found to detect 73% of the immune-fluorescence test positive cases correctly and able to detect 47% of the immune-fluorescence test negative cases correctly.

Another study shows the positivity rate of ANA detected by IIF and Anti-CCP was significantly different (87.8% and 73.17%, respectively, $P < 0.01$), but the positivity rate of anti-dsDNA was similar between IIF and ELISA (77.19% and 71.93%, respectively, $P > 0.05$). The percent agreement between the two testing methods with different cutoff values of ANA and anti-dsDNA showed significant differences ($P < 0.01$) ^{13,14}.

IIF and ELISA both are important but IIF has more sensitivity than ELISA but yet not IIF is not commonly practiced in our country. So this study results would helpful to our immunological and microbiological field for screening of CTD by indirect Immunofluorescence technique.

References

- Hansson, H., G. Trowald-Wigh, and A. Karlsson-Parra. Detection of antinuclear antibodies by indirect immunofluorescence in dog sera: comparison of rat liver tissue and human epithelial-2 cells as antigenic substrate. *J. Vet. Intern. Med* 1996 vol. 10: pp. 199-203
- Prost, A. C., et al.. Comparing HEP-2 cell line with rat liver in routine screening test for antinuclear and antinucleolar antibodies in autoimmune disease. *Ann. Biol. Clin.* 1987, vol. 45 pp. :610-617.
- Emlen, W., and L. O'Neill.. Clinical significance of antinuclear antibodies. *Arthr. Rheum.* 1997, vol. 40: pp. 612-1618
- Gniewek, RA ., DP. Stites, T.M. McHugh, JF. Hilton, and M. Nakagawa. Comparison of antinuclear antibody testing methods: immunofluorescence assay versus enzyme immunoassay. *Clin. Diagn. Lab. Immunol.* 1997, vol. 4: pp. 185-188.
- Jaskowski, T. D., C. Schroder, T. B. Martins, C. L. Mouritsen, C. M. Litwino, and H. R. Hill.. Screening for antinuclear antibodies by enzyme immunoassay. *Am. J. Clin. Pathol* 1996, vol. 105 , pp. 468-473.
- Cohen PL, ,Systemic Autoimmunity, In: Psul WE, editor, *Fundamental. immunology*, 4th ed Lippincott Raven. Philadelphia New York, 2003, pp. 1067-1083
- Casals Ps, Friour JG, Lynn LL. Significance of Antibody to DNA in SLE. *Arthritis Rheum.* 1964 , vol ;7:, pp. 379-389.
- Gonzalez EN, Rothfield FN.1967,'Immunoglobulin class and pattern of nuclear fluorescence in SLE, *N Eng J Med* vol, 274, pp. 1333-1338.
- Reichlin M, Mattioli M. Correlation of a precipitin reaction to a RNA protein antigen and a low prevalence of nephritis in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus . *N Engl J Med* 1972 vol. ;286: pp. 1194-51.
- Husain M, Neff J. Daily E, Townsend J. Lucas F. Antinuclear antibodies- clinical significance of titres and fluorescent pattern. *AM. J. Clin .Path.* 1974 vol. ;61: pp. 59-65.
- Bhuyan UN. Malaviya AN .Antinuclear antibodies and pattern of nuclear immunofluorescences in SLE and other collagen vascular diseases. *Indian sJ.Med. Res.*1976 vol. ;64: pp. 895-902.
- Naraynan S, Malaviya AN, Bhuyan UN. Profile of patients with serum antinuclear antibody. *Indian J. Med. Res.* 1976; vol. 64: pp. 1769-1773.

Health Education Intervention on Hand Washing in a selected Primary School Children

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Abstract

It was a quasi experimental type of study with the objective of finding to assess the effects of health education intervention on hand washing among the primary school students. The study was carried out 75 students of a selected Bari gaon Primary school, Dhamrai, Dhaka. Students were respondents from class four and five. Education intervention was planned, organised and conducted on baseline data. Intervention method was making some lesson plan by the student group using some poster, flip chart, role-play, etc. The findings showed that out of 75 students 42(56%) were female and rest of them 33(44%) were male. Majority of the respondents 48(64%) were in the age of 8-10 years and 27(36%) were in the age of 10-12 years. Out of 75 respondents 32(43%) were muslim and 43(57%) were hindus. Out of 75 respondent's parent 29(39%) were illiterate, 24(32%) were primary pass, 17(23%) were SSC pass, 04(5%) were HSC pass and only 01(1%) were graduate. Out of 75 respondent's parent occupation 15(20%) were business, 14(19%) were service, 21(28%) were day labour, and 25(33%) were others occupation. Out of 75 respondent's parent monthly income 08(11%) were less than 5000 taka, 51(68%) were in between 5000-10000 taka, 16(21%) were above 10000 taka. Among all respondents 97% told hand wash before meal, 80% after defecation, 100% told hand wash with soap, 9% told with ash. Before intervention only 11% told hand wash for 20 seconds but after intervention which were improved to 86%, and regarding steps of hand washing, before intervention only 1% told eight steps of hand washing but after intervention which were improved to 100%. At the end of the study it may concluded that though the intervention period was too short to grip but it is effective in the long run.

Introduction:

Hand washing with soap is a low-cost intervention of documented efficacy that has been of proven worth for more than a century, but has often been neglected for more glamorous, expensive, and less effective. Hand washing is simple and common practice in our daily life. Sometimes we do it carefully and sometimes carelessly but we think proper hand washing is a very

simple weapon to defend deadly enemies. Improving hand washing practices remain one of the central challenges for the public health community in the 21st century¹.

Each year over 5 million children in developing countries die from either diarrhoea disease or acute respiratory infections (ARI)². Around the world, hand washing practice with soap is the most effective ways to prevent diarrhoea diseases, ARI, Swine flue, Avian flue etc. Hand washing with soap after contact with faces and before contact with food can reduce rates of diarrhoea among the under five by 42-47%^{3,4}.

As estimated 1.9 million children less than 5 years of age die annually from diarrhoeal disease and an additional 2 million die of pneumonia. Small scale studies in settings where diarrhoea and respiratory disease are leading causes of death show that households that receive intensive hand washing promotion report less diarrhoea and respiratory disease compared with control households. However, in settings where diarrhoea is an important cause of child mortality, the prevalence of hand washing with soap after contact with feces as assessed by structured observation is typically <30%. A primary objective of intervention is to increase the promotion of persons who wash their hands at key times, i.e., before preparing of food, before eating, before feeding a child, after defecation and after cleaning a child's anus. Diarrhoea and ARI are responsible for the

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majority of child death in developing countries specially in Bangladesh. Only hand washing can reduce morbidity and mortality by 42% of the affected individuals. Proper hand washing can prevent 33% occurrence of communicable diseases⁵.

Every year, Ghana suffers an estimated 9 million episode of diarrhoea and 8400 diarrhoea death among children less than 5 years, at an estimated annual cost of US\$3 million. Traditionally hygiene promotion programmers have relied on an educational approach, operating on the assumption that simply increasing hygiene knowledge understanding of biomedical models of disease transmission, and providing hand washing facilities with result in improved hand washing behavior. Many hospital based studies suggest such intuition represents over-simplification⁶. Improvement of hand washing behavior among health care staff when a hospital moved to new premises with a sink beside each and every bed⁷. In this study we revisited some of the factors. We hypothesized that mothers hand washing practice would be determined by factors both extrinsic and intrinsic to her. Extrinsic factor investigated that were expected facilitate or constitute barriers to practicing hand washing included: the site of defecation, the method of stool disposal, and the age of index child. Intrinsic factors included mothers formal education, her health consciousness and knowledge of the most important times to wash her hands, her activeness to the index child and her disgust score⁸.

Food production workers and food service personnel must be taught to use correct hand washing by management, in preparation for work. Regulatory authorities do not require the use of fingernail brush; however correct use of fingernail brush to wash hands and finger tips the best way to assure removal transient microorganisms. The incidence of diarrhoea in two day care centres with a hand washing program was half that of two control centres for an entire 35 week study period. Employees in the hand washing program washed their hands before handling food after arriving at the day care centre, used the toilet, were diapered, or prepared to eat, employees washed their hands bar soap paper towels⁹.

The effectiveness of the simple intervention of hand washing with soap and water in preventing the spread of shigelosis was investigated. Secondary infection rates within families in Bangladesh due to transfer of pathogenic bacteria decreased, when people were taught to wash their hands after defecation and before eating. The study population was comprised of confirmed cases of shigelosis. These and matched

controls were followed up for 10 days. Several pieces of soap and earthenware pitchers for storing water were provided to the study families and they were advised to wash their hands with soap and water after defecation and before eating. Compliance was daily monitored by observing the size of the soap and residual water. Rectal swabs of contact of both of the groups were obtained daily for culture. The secondary infection rate was 10.1% in the study group and 14.2% in the control group. These results suggest that the hand washing has a positive interrupting effect, even in sanitary environments¹⁰.

In prospectively designed studies with appropriate control groups, interventions that promote regular hand washing with soap consistently reduce both diarrhoeal and respiratory diseases¹¹.

Materials and Methods:

This Quasi-experimental study on health education intervention on hand washing among primary school students was carried out at the Barigaon koilas charda high school, Dhamrai Thana of Dhaka District. Study Period was from 5th March 2010 to 30th April 2010. 75 students of Class iv & v of Barigaon koilas charda high school were selected for the study. The sample was collected by Non-probability Purposive sampling technique. A pretested structured questionnaire was used for collection of data. Data were collected by the researcher himself through direct interview of the respondents. After collection of base line data health education intervention program was conducted by preparing a lesson plan according to the objectives, after that post intervention data was collected. Data analysis was done manually by sample statistical technique and Presented in table, pie chart, bar diagram etc.

Result:

Table 01: Distribution of respondent by the knowledge on Causes for hand washing pre&post intervention

N=75

Causes of hand washing	Pre-intervention		Post-intervention	
	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage
For personal care	03	04%	12	16%
For cleanliness	45	60%	75	100%
To prevent contamination	27	36%	46	61%
Others	02	03%	00	0%

Table: 1 Shows among 75 respondents 3 (4%) told hand washes for personal care, 45 (60%) for cleanliness, 27 (36%) for prevention of contamination, 02(3%) for other purpose, before intervention. Some respondents answered two or more at a time so the total exceed 100%.After intervention which were improved to 12 (16%), 75 (100%), 46 (61%), 00 (0%) respectively and all the respondents known about the causes for hand washing.

Table 02: Distribution of respondent by the knowledge on Timing of hand washing pre&posts intervention

N=75

Timing of hand washing	Pre-intervention		Post-intervention	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Before meal	73	97	46	61
After defecation	60	80	75	100
After cleaning latrine	23	31	75	100
Don't know	00	00	00	00

Table: 02 Shows among 75 respondents 73(97%) told hand washes before meal, 60(80%) after defecation, 23(31%) after cleaning latrine, 00(0%) didn't knew the timing of hand washing, before intervention. Some respondents answered two or more at a time so the total exceed 100%.After intervention which were improved to 46(61%), 75(100%), 75(100%), 00(0%) respectively and all the respondents known about the timing of hand washing.

Table 03: Distribution of respondent by the knowledge on Materials used in hand washing pre&post intervention

N=75

Materials of hand washing	Pre-intervention		Post-intervention	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Soap	75	100	75	100
Ash	07	09	14	19
Soil	02	03	00	00
Only water	02	03	00	00

Table: 3 Shows among 75 respondents 75(100%) told hand washes with soap, 07(9%) with ash, 02(03%) with soil, 02(3%) with only water, before intervention. Some respondents answered two or more at a time so the total exceed 100%.After intervention which were improved to 75(100%), 14(19%), 00(0%), 00(0%) respectively and all the respondents known about the appropriate materials to used in hand washing.

Table 04: Distribution of respondent by the knowledge on Duration Of hand washing pre&post intervention

N=75

Duration of hand washing	Pre-intervention		Post-intervention	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
20 seconds	08	11	64	86
1 minutes	33	44	03	4
2 minutes	30	40	04	5
3 minutes	04	5	04	5

Table: 04 Shows among 75 respondents 08(11%) told hand washes for 20 seconds, 33(44%) for 1 minute, 30(40%) for 2 minutes, 04(5%) for 3 minutes, before intervention. After intervention which were improved to 64(86%), 03(4%), 04(5%), 04(5%) respectively and most of the respondents known about the appropriate duration of hand washing.

Table 05: Distribution of respondent by the knowledge on Disease transmission due to improper hand Washing pre&post intervention

N=75

Transmitted disease	Pre-intervention		Post-intervention	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Typhoid	14	19	75	100
Diarrhoea	70	93	75	100
Dysentery	36	48	73	97
Others	06	8	00	00

Table: 05 Shows among 75 respondents 14(19%) told typhoid transmitted due to improper hand washing, 70(93%) told diarrhoea transmitted due to improper hand washing, 36(48%) told dysentery transmitted due to improper hand washing, 06(8%) told other diseases, before intervention. Some respondents answered two or more at a time so the total exceed 100%.After intervention which were improved to 75(100%), 75(1%), 73(97%), 00(0%) respectively and most of the

respondents known about the diseases which transmitted due to improper hand washing.

Table: 06 Distribution of respondent by the knowledge on Steps Of hand washing pre&post intervention

N=75

Steps of hand washing	Pre-intervention		Post-intervention	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Six	29	39	00	00
Seven	04	5	00	00
Eight	01	1	75	100
Don't know	41	55	00	00
Total	75	100	75	100

Table 06: Shows among 75 respondents 29(39%) told six steps of hand washing, 04(5%) told seven steps, 01(1%) told eight, 41(55%) didn't knew, before intervention. After intervention which were improved to 00(0%), 00(0%), 75(100%), 00(0%) respectively and all of the respondents known about the steps of hand washing.

Discussion:

This quasi experimental study was conducted among the primary school children of the Bari gaon primary school, Dhamrai with a view to assess knowledge about hand washing. A total 75 students were interviewed using structured questionnaire in class iv and v.

Out of 75 respondents 3(4%) told hand washes for personal care, 45(60%) for cleanliness, 27(36%) for prevention of contamination, 02(3%) for other purpose, before intervention. Some respondents answered two or more at a time so the total exceed 100%. After intervention which were improved to 12(16%), 75(100%), 46(61%), 00(0%) respectively and all the respondents known about the causes for hand washing. (Table:01)

This study revealed among 75 respondents 73(97%) told hand washes before meal, 60(80%) after defecation, 23(31%) after cleaning latrine, 00(0%) didn't knew the timing of hand washing, before intervention. Some respondents answered two or more at a time so the total exceed 100%. After intervention which were improved to 46(61%), 75(100%), 75(100%), 00(0%) respectively and all the respondents known about the timing of hand washing. (Table:02)

This study shows among 75 respondents 75(100%) told hand washes with soap, 07(9%) with ash, 02(03%) with soil, 02(3%) with only water, before intervention. Some respondents answered two or more at a time so the total exceed 100%. After intervention which were improved to 75(100%), 14(19%), 00(0%), 00(0%) respectively and all the respondents known about the appropriate materials to used in hand washing. (Table:03)

This study shows among 75 respondents 08(11%) told hand washes for 20 seconds, 33(44%) for 1 minute, 30(40%) for 2 minutes, 04(5%) for 3 minutes, before intervention. After intervention which were improved to 64(86%), 03(4%), 04(5%), 04(5%) respectively and most of the respondents known about the appropriate duration of hand washing. (Table:04)

This study shows among 75 respondents 14(19%) told typhoid transmitted due to improper hand washing, 70(93%) told diarrhea transmitted due to improper hand washing, 36(48%) told dysentery transmitted due to improper hand washing, 06(8%) told other diseases, before intervention. Some respondents answered two or more at a time so the total exceed 100%. After intervention which were improved to 75(100%), 75(1%), 73(97%), 00(0%) respectively and most of the respondents known about the diseases which transmitted due to improper hand washing. (Table:05)

This study shows among 75 respondents 29(39%) told six steps of hand washing, 04(5%) told seven steps, 01(1%) told eight, 41(55%) didn't knew, before intervention. After intervention which were improved to 00(0%), 00(0%), 75(100%), 00(0%) respectively and all of the respondents known about the steps of hand washing. (Table:06)

Conclusion:

The population of Bangladesh is increasing so fast day by day as a result, most of the people come to school from different religious and different school place there is no proper hand washing facilities. After all majority low income people were live in village. This study shows that out of 75, 27(36%) students used soap for hand washing after defecation and 33(42%) did not used no materials for hand washing after defecation. Before intervention out of 75, 30(41%) knew that diarrhoeal disease could be prevented by proper hand washing where as after intervention 54(71%) knows diarrhoeal disease can be prevented by proper hand washing after defecation. So from this experience it is observed that the health education component must be integrated with all our health programmes for their effective

implementation. There is a great need and profitability in employing educational approach to solve our essential health problems. This study shows there is more chance of the success in solving our health problems. The Educational approach is very much helpful in eliminating ignorance of people and creating strong motivation to adopt the appropriate health practice. The study also demonstrates the importance of involvement of professional health education in all stage of health problem administration. From this study, in conclusion we feel that if appropriate health education programme is developed and attach to our essential health problems, we are confident that we can achieve our millennium development goals of health sector 2015.

References:

1. Shahid NR, et al. Hand Washing with Soap Reduces Diarrhoea and Spread of Bacterial Pathogens in a Bangladesh Village. *J Diarrhoeal Disease* 1996 Jun; 14(2): 85-89
2. Alvaran Ms, But [http://www.Global hand washing.org/country20%act/Attachments/GhanaProgMaster.doc]
3. Curtis V, Cairncross S. Effect of washing hands with soap on diarrhoea risk in the community: a systemic review. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases* (2003), 3: 275-281.
4. Libby SP, et al. Effect of intensive hand washing Promotion on childhood diarrhoea in high risk communities in Pakistan. *Journal of American Medical Association* (2004) 291:2547-54.
5. Luby SP, et al. Household Characteristics Associated with Hand Washing with soap in Rural Bangladesh. *Am. J. Trop. Med. Hyg.* 81(5), 2009, pp. 882-887
6. Pittet D, Hugonnet S, Harbarth S, et al. Effectiveness of a hospital-wide programme to improve compliance with hand hygiene. *The Lancet* (2000) 356: 1307-12.
7. Preston GA, Larson EL, Sarm WE. The effect of private isolation rooms on patient care practices, colonization and infection in an intensive care unit. *American Journal of Medicine* (1981) 70: 641-5. [Cross Ref][ISI][Medicine]
8. Curtis V, Aunger R, Rabie T. Evidence that disgust evolved to protect from Risk of disease. *Proceedings of the Royal Society Biology Letters* (2004) 272:S131-3.
9. Rabie T, Curtis V. Hand washing and risk of respiratory infections: a quantitative Systemic review. *Tropical Medicine and international Health* (2006)
10. http://www.hi-tm.com/Documents/Safehands.html.
11. Luby SP, et al. Difficulties in Maintaining Improved Handwashing Behavior, Karachi, Pakistan. *Am. J. Trop. Med. Hyg.* 81(1), 2009, pp.140-145.

Review on Dental implants Success and Failures

MM Hasan

Abstract:

Success and failure of dental implants are completely dependent on the osseointegration around a dental implant. This paper reviews the success and failure of dental implant and found that no single criteria can fulfil the success of dental implant. Fixity of the fixer in the bone that is lack of mobility of the fixer in the bone is the prime factor for osseointegration and resulting in success. Implant can be failed due to hard tissue or soft tissue problem. Patients over age 60, smoked, uncontrolled diabetes or head and neck radiation, or were postmenopausal and on hormone replacement therapy are the risk factor for implant failure.

Introduction:

Dental implants are inert, alloplastic materials set up in the Jaw to replace the lost or missing teeth. This procedure replaces the need for dental bridges to replace the lost teeth which had to involve the sound teeth for replacement of the lost one. The most common type of dental implant is endosseous comprising a discrete, single implant unit (screw- or cylinder-shaped are the most typical forms) placed within a drilled space within dentoalveolar or basal bone. Commercially pure titanium or titanium alloy or the vitalinium are the common constituents of dental implants. However, alternative materials include ceramics such as aluminium oxide and other alloys (gold and nicklechrome vanadium). Generally, endosseous implants have a coating which may comprise plasma-sprayed titanium or a layer of hydroxyapatite to enhance early osseointegration. Osseointegration is the basic principle of dental implants success. 'Osseointegration' was discovered by Branemark in 1969 when he observed that a piece of titanium embedded in rabbit bone became firmly anchored and difficult to remove.¹ Following one year of observation, no inflammation was detected in the peri-implant bone, meanwhile soft tissue had formed an attachment to the metal and bone to the titanium.² The Branemark system of dental implants was introduced in 1971.³ After endosseous implant fixtures are surgically inserted into bone, the process of osseointegration begins. Osseointegration is considered 'a direct, structural and functional connection between organised vital bone and the surface of a titanium implant, capable of bearing the functional load. This is possible as the titanium surface oxide layer (mainly titanium dioxide) is biocompatible, reactive and

spontaneously forms calcium-phosphateapatite.⁴ Furthermore, the titanium oxide surface of implants achieves a union with the superficial gingivae restricting the ingress of oral microorganisms. Consequently, the implant/soft tissue interface is similar to the union between tooth and gingivae.^{4,5,6}

Dental implants are predominantly placed in dental chamber and in outpatient department, commonly in general dental practice under local anaesthesia. Success rates are reported as being as high as 90-95%.^{7,8} This paper reviews endosseous dental implants and factors associated with success and failure.

Success and failure

No single criteria can full fill the success of dental implant. A variety of factors have been proposed for the successful osseointegration of dental implant have been proposed.⁹ Of these, a lack of mobility is of prime importance as 'loosening' is the most often cited reason for implant fixture removal.¹⁰ Adell reported the success rate of 895 implant fixtures over an observational period of 5-9 years after placement.⁷ Eighty-one percent of maxillary and 91% of mandibular implants remained stable. Despite high success rates, implant fixture failure may occur and is defined as 'the inadequacy of the host tissue to establish or maintain osseointegration'.⁸ One review suggested that 2% of implants failed to achieve osseointegration following placement.⁹ Using a meta-analysis, failure rates for Branemark dental implants were 7.7% (excluding bone grafts) over five years.¹¹ Interestingly, failure rates within edentulous patients were almost double those for partially dentate patients (7.6% versus 3.8%).¹¹ Peri-implantitis is an inflammation around a functioning osseointegrated implant, resulting in loss of supporting bone.¹² Failing dental implants gives the Signs similar to that of tooth with periodontitis in both clinically and radiographically.¹³ This involves measuring clinical parameters including peri-implant loss of gingival attachment, bleeding on probing, plaque/gingivitis indices, suppuration and mobility. Other relevant assessments include a peri-implant radiographic

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examination and microbiological sampling. Periimplantitis has been reported in 5-8% of cases within selected implant systems.

Classification of failures

Implant failures can be categorised as early or late. Early failures occur before osseointegration takes place but late failures occurs after prosthetic rehabilitation.⁹ Factors affecting early failure of dental implants may be broadly classified as: implant-, patient- and surgical technique/environment-related. Late failures may be subclassified into late-early or late-delayed depending on whether they occur during or after the first year of loading. Late-delayed failures are likely due to changes in loading conditions in relation to the quality/volume of bone and peri implantitis.

Implants failure can also be described as failing or failed. A failing implant demonstrates a progressive loss of supporting bone but is clinically immobile, whereas a failed implant is clinically mobile. When an implant has failed, removal is recommended while a failing implant may be salvaged if it is diagnosed early and treated appropriately.

Implant can be failed due to hard tissue problem or soft tissue problem. An implant compromised by soft-tissue problems has a more favourable prognosis than one undergoing bone loss.¹⁴ Nevertheless, infection originating in the soft tissues may potentially progress deeper into the bone and undermine the osseointegration process.^{15,16} Some of the most frequent causes of soft tissue infection during the healing period involve residual suture material, poorly seated cover screws, protruding implants and trauma from inadequately relieved dentures or occlusal trauma from opposing teeth.¹⁷

Moreover patients who were over age 60, smoked, had a history of diabetes or head and neck radiation, or were postmenopausal and on hormone replacement therapy experienced significantly increased implant failure compared with healthy patients.¹⁸

Despite a variety of therapeutic options, infected implants are difficult to treat and usually require removal.¹⁹ Oral agents such as doxycycline, clindamycin, co-amoxiclav, penicillin V, amoxicillin and a combination of amoxicillin and metronidazole have been recommended.

Conclusion

Overall, dental implant failure is low and there are no absolute contraindications to implant placement. Conditions that were found to be correlated with an increased risk of failure should be considered during treatment planning and factored into the informed consent process

References

1. Worthington P. Introduction: history of implants. In:forthington P, Lang BR, Rubenstein JE, editors. Osseointegration in dentistry: an overview. 2nd ed. Illinois: Quintessence; 2003. p. 2.
2. Branemark PI. Osseointegration and its experimental background. *J Prosthet Dent* 1983;50:399e410
3. Hobo S, Ichida E, Garcia LT. Osseointegration and occlusal rehabilitation. Tokyo: Quintessence; 1990. pp. 3-4
4. Hansson HA, Albrektsson T, Branemark PI. Structural aspects of the interface between tissue and titanium implants. *J Prosthet Dent* 1983;50:108e113.
5. Branemark PI, Adell R, Breine U, Hansson BO, Lindstrom J, Ohlsson A. Intraosseous anchorage of dental prostheses. I. Experimental studies. *Scand J Plast Reconstr Surg* 1969;3:81e100.
6. Albrektsson T, Branemark PI, Hansson HA, Lindstrom J. Osseointegrated titanium implants. Requirements for ensuring a long-lasting direct bone-to-implant anchorage in man. *Acta Orthop Scand* 1981;52:155e170.
7. Adell R, Lekholm U, Rockler B, Branemark PI. A 15-year study of osseointegrated implants in the treatment of the edentulous jaw. *Int J Oral Surg* 1981;10:387-416
8. Quirynen M, De Soete, van Steenberghe D. Infectious risk for oral implants: a review of the literature. *Clin Oral Implants Res* 2000;13:1-19
9. Albrektsson T, Zarb GA, Worthington P, Eriksson AR. The long-term efficacy of currently used dental implants: a review and proposed criteria of success. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants* 1986;1:11-25.
10. Linden R, Pihakari A, Pera la A, Mäkelä A. The 2002 dental implant yearbook. The Finnish dental implant register. Helsinki: National Agency for Medicines; 2003.
11. Esposito M, Hirsch JM, Lekholm U, Thomsen P. Biological factors contributing to failures of osseointegrated implants (I). Success criteria and epidemiology. *Eur J Oral Sci* 1998; 106:527-551.
12. Mombelli A, Lang NP. The diagnosis and treatment of periimplantitis. *Periodontol* 2000 1998;17:63-76
13. Bragger U, Hugel-Pisoni C, Burgin WB, Buser D, Lang NP. Correlations between radiographic, clinical and mobility parameters after loading of oral implants with fixed partial dentures: a 2-year longitudinal study. *Clin Oral Implants Res* 1996;7:230-239.
14. Meffert RM. Maintenance and treatment of the failing and failing implant. *J Indiana Dent Assoc* 1994;73:22-24.
15. Tonetti MS, Schmid J. Pathogenesis of implant failures. *Periodontol* 200 94;4:127-138.
16. Kaiser AB. Antimicrobial prophylaxis in surgery. *N Engl J Med* 1986;315:1129- 1138.
17. Esposito M, Hirsch J, Lekholm U, Thomsen P. Differential diagnosis and treatment strategies for biologic complications and failing oral implants: a review of the literature. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants* 1999;14:473-490.
18. S.K. Chuang, L.J. Wei C.W. Douglass T.B. Dodson Risk Factors for Dental Implant Failure *J Dent Res* 81(8) 2002. 572-577
19. Esposito M, Hirsch JM, Lekholm U, Thomsen P. Biological factors contributing to failures of osseointegrated oral implants. Etiopathogenesis. *Eur J Oral Sci* 1998;106:721-764.

Childhood Obesity: A Challenge for Pediatric Dentistry

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Abstract

The link between childhood oral diseases and obesity is demonstrated by their increasing prevalence, potential cause and effect relationship, the significant deleterious effect on the child's present and future oral and systemic health, and the influence of obesity on conscious sedation. Deleterious effects of dental caries and obesity on the systemic condition are clear; may potentiate each other, and facilitate the development and progress of chronic or acute systemic conditions. This article is to review the causes of childhood obesity, discuss the relevance of obesity to dental disease, and highlight some of the actions pediatric dentists should adopt. As a pediatric dentist, we have a commitment to understand, prevent and intervene in the development of both obesity and dental disease.

Keywords: Obesity, Challenges, Pediatric Dentistry

Introduction

The prevalence of obesity in children has increased worldwide; Childhood obesity presents both immediate and long-term health risks such as orthopaedic consequences, hypertension, hypercholesterolaemia, insulin resistance, and adult obesity. Oral health is strongly influenced by the intake of sugar-rich foods, and high dental decay scores are associated with an unbalanced diet.¹ Sugar-rich diets have been associated with various health problems such as obesity, bone loss, and bone fractures.² Dental caries during childhood continues to be a significant public health concern, while childhood obesity is increasingly being cited as a major public health problem. Recent studies have identified an association between dental caries and obesity in childhood, and have suggested that obese children are at an increased risk for dental caries.^{3,4} Few studies on the relationship between obesity and dental decay have been published to date. A recent literature review indicated that three studies have provided convincing evidence of a direct correlation between

obesity and dental caries.² The purpose of this article is to review the causes of childhood obesity, discuss the relevance of obesity to dental disease, and highlight some of the actions pediatric dentists should adopt.

Obesity

Obesity is a disease process in which energy intakes exceed energy requirements resulting in the deposition of body fat. Obesity is defined as an excess of body fat and has both genetic and environmental origins. Although environmental obesity conjures images of indulgence, particularly on high-fat, sweetened treats, and limited physical activity, biological adaptation and food culture may be more responsible.^{5,6}

Obesity is demonstrated by their increasing prevalence, potential cause and effect relationship, the significant deleterious effect on the child's present and future oral and systemic health, and the influence of obesity on conscious sedation. While some reports suggest a connection between caries and obesity others do not, and it is unclear if they correlate or they just coexist since they have common etiologic and/or facilitating factors. Deleterious effects of dental caries and obesity on the systemic condition are clear, may potentiate each other, and facilitate the development and progress of chronic or acute systemic conditions. Obesity may interfere with the possibility to sedate patients because of potential breathing problems, or modify the effect of the sedative agents. Health providers should be aware of the increasing challenge posed by the correlations between dental caries, obesity, oral and systemic diseases. Furthermore, pediatric dentistry should team with other health professions in order to cooperate in

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the prevention and treatment of these diseases.⁷

Dental Caries

Dental caries is a disease process in which repeated exposure to acids produced during bacterial fermentation of carbohydrates erodes the enamel. The erosion is progressive and can lead to cavitation of the enamel and, thereafter, of the dentin. Although necessary, the dietary component of the disease process is difficult to quantify. Sugars, modified starches and starches are all subject to fermentation; sugared soda-pop, confections and starches baked with sugars are considered highly cariogenic.⁸ Dietary habits, that is, when and how the beverage or food is consumed, can modify this risk with frequent consumption of sugars thought to increase risk.⁹

Obesity and Dental Caries

Although the relationship between obesity and dental caries in children needs further exploration, it is clear that there are *common denominators* that both diseases share. The true etiology of both obesity and dental caries is complex and multifactorial. Many of the contributing factors are rooted in evolving changes in lifestyle and the internal body as well as external environment. Negative changes in eating, decreased activity patterns, increased frequency of snacking, and increased consumption of fermentable carbohydrates are common in both obesity and caries in children.

The dietary habits of children are a significant contributor to obesity and dental caries epidemics. It is well established that dental caries and frequent ingestion of refined carbohydrates are highly correlated.¹⁰ It is appropriate to hypothesize that overweight might also be a marker for dental caries in children and teenagers. Soft drink consumption too, has been associated with increased calorie intake, increased body weight, pediatric obesity and dental caries.¹¹

Evidence for the Role of Obesity in Dental Disease

Bailleul-Forestier I et al concluded that there was a significant association between BMI and decayed, missing and filled teeth (DMFT) indices ($P=0.01$) in the severely obese group of adolescents under study. The obese adolescents were more likely to have caries than the non-obese ones.¹² Similar results were found by

Hilgers KK et al that the mean caries average for permanent molars significantly increased with increased BMI, even after adjusting for age and gender.¹³ A Swedish study examined the relationship between dental caries and risk factors for atherosclerosis in nearly 200 15-year-olds in one small urban community. The study reported that children with a dental decay score greater than 9 had significantly higher BMI values than caries-free children.¹⁴

Role of the Pediatric Dentist

Pediatric dentists should be familiar with the specific dental and medical findings routinely associated with the obese patient and have a basic knowledge of how to screen for obesity and when to provide referrals to the pediatrician. Dietary counseling by pediatric dentists may be centered on assessment of dietary interventions related to:

- (1) Presence of Early Childhood Caries (ECC)
- (2) Frequency of and type of snacking
- (3) Judicious soft drink consumption
- (4) Overall nutrition status
- (5) Levels of physical activity
- (6) Socio-economic status and
- (7) Parent lifestyle (sedentary/active, eating habits, working times)

Generally, a dental history is restricted to oral hygiene concerns and the orientation of the questioning does not give clues to the child's risk of overweight or reasons for obesity if it already exists. The addition of health history questions regarding parental concern about a child's weight or height, diet, hours of television viewing (screen-time), and exercise habits can help the pediatric dentist make a more accurate assessment of a patient's risk for obesity.

The matter of addressing a child's weight with parents is a more difficult challenge that needs to be based on the comfort level of the dentist. One method may be to incorporate this information into an oral health card that can be reviewed at each recall appointment to call attention to and document clinical findings. Adding BMI to the other dental health information of the child that is reviewed with the parent may be an easier way to objectively present the information. It would also be suitable to refer a high BMI patient to a pediatrician and

dietician for consultation. Pediatric dentists sensitized to the risks associated with improper diet and dietary habits can make a positive impact by encouraging parents to promote healthy lifestyles and dietary habits, while discouraging those poor dietary and sedentary habits which increase the risk of obesity and dental caries.¹⁵

Challenging Policies for Pediatric Dentistry

The dentist could consider developing/revising policies and procedures that focus on protecting the child's health:

- Documentation of the child's medical history is especially important. Has the child had respiratory problems? Has the child been seen in the emergency department? If so, for what reasons? Medications, including OTC drugs, should be carefully noted.
- The dentist should ensure that contact information is readily available for all practitioners who may be involved with the child's medical care. Is the child seeing an allergist, pulmonologist, diabetic specialist? Since these children are more likely to be under the care of specialist(s), the dentist should specifically ask for this information, as the parent may provide only the name of a pediatrician.
- A policy that requires consultation with the child's physician before any invasive procedure is planned should be also be implemented. Learning whether or not the significantly overweight child has been screened for diabetes is essential. In addition, feedback from the child's pediatrician may also be useful in convincing a parent that dental care should be provided in a hospital versus a dental setting. The pediatrician may also provide suggestions about staging elements of the treatment plan.
- The dentist may want to implement a policy that requires blood pressure monitoring both before and, for extended treatment plans, periodically throughout the procedure. When should the dentist consider a blood pressure reading too high? Under what circumstances will the dentist want to consult with the child's physician? What should be the hypertensive/hypotensive limits that preclude dental treatment? Only dentists can and should determine these limits.
- If drugs or medication will be dispensed or administered, dentists should consider using a scale to determine the child's actual weight. Parents are not always the most accurate reporters of their child's weight, especially if the child has a weight problem. A scale can prevent this type of misinformation and its consequent risk to the child.
- Pharmacists can also provide valuable information about drug dosing for overweight pediatric patients. It is important when working with overweight children that dentists have a very safe comfort zone for initiating drugs, use of antagonists and calculating recovery times.
- Does the child have shortness of breath upon exertion, i.e., walking into the building? Does the child wheeze or give other indications of possible respiratory or pulmonary complications? What screening processes will the dentist consistently use for children with weight issues?
- Dentists know that conscious sedation is often more challenging when the patient is a child. For the overweight child, will additional or perhaps more frequent monitoring procedures need to be in place? Should any changes be made in the clinical assessment used to determine at which point the child may safely be sent home?¹⁶

Conclusion

The challenge of providing dental care to overweight children is not an issue that can safely be ignored. That said, the processes by which dentists determine how best to protect these young patients are unlikely to require an entirely new treatment construct. Current policies and procedures should be assessed. Based on research and assessment, current processes may need to be reconfigured in order to ensure these patients' safety and comfort. The process requires time and some documentation. It may, however, be responsible for saving a child's life. As a pediatric dentist, we have a commitment to understand, prevent and intervene in the development of both obesity and dental disease. As clinicians in frequent contact with children and their parents, we also have the perfect opportunity to do so.

References

1. Larsson B, Johansson I, Ericson T. Prevalence of caries in adolescents in relation to diet. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol* 1992; 20: 133–137.

2. Kantovitz KR, Pascon FM, Rontani RM, Gaviao MB. Obesity and dental caries. A systematic review. *Oral Health Prev Dent* 2006; 4: 137–144.
3. Reifsnider E, Mobley C, Mendez DB. Childhood obesity and early childhood caries in a WIC population. *J Multicultural Nurs Health* 2004;10:24–31.
4. Tuomi T. Pilot study on obesity in caries prediction. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol* 1989;17:289–91.
5. Carlos Poston WS II, Foreyt JP. Obesity is an environmental issue. *Atherosclerosis* 1999;146:201–9.
6. Nicklas TA, Baranowski T, Cullen KW, Berenson G. Eating patterns, dietary quality and obesity. *J Am Coll Nutr* 2001;20:599–608.
7. Bimstein E, Katz J. Obesity in Children: A Challenge that Pediatric Dentistry Should not Ignore – Review of the Literature. *Journal of Clinical Pediatric Dentistry* 2009;34(2): 103-106.
8. Marshall TA, Levy SM, Broffitt B, Warren JJ, Eichenberger- Gilmore JM, Burns TL et al. Dental caries and beverage consumption in young children. *Pediatrics* 2003;112:e184–91.
9. Marshall TA, Broffitt B, Eichenberger-Gilmore J, Warren JJ, Cunningham MA, Levy SM. The roles of meal, snack and daily total food and beverage exposures on caries experience in young children. *J Public Health Dent* 2005;65:166–73.
10. Sreebny L. Sugar availability, sugar consumption, and dental caries. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol* 1982; 10:1-7.
11. Gillis LJ, Bar-Or O. Food away from home, sugar sweetened drink consumption and juvenile obesity. *J Am Coll Nutr* 2003; 22:539–545.
12. Bailleul-Forestier I, Lopes K, Souames M, Azoguy-Levy S, Frelut M, Boy-Lefevre M. Caries experience in a severely obese adolescent population. *Int J Paediatr Dent* 2007; 17:358-363.
13. Hilgers KK, Kinane DE, Scheetz JP. Association between childhood obesity and smooth-surface caries in posterior teeth: a preliminary study. *Pediatr Dent*. 2006 Jan-Feb; 28:23-8.
14. Johansson I, Hallmans G, Ericson T. Relationship between dental caries and risk factors for atherosclerosis in Swedish adolescents? *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol* 1995; 23:205-210.
15. Chandna, P., Adlakha V.K. Childhood Obesity and Dental Disease: Combined Role of the Pediatrician and Pediatric Dentist. *Journal of Pediatric Sciences*. 2010;6:57
16. Roman K. R. The Overweight Child in the Dental Chair: Risk Management Considerations. *Pediatric Dentistry* Nov 2003; 32-33.

Orthodontic treatment of Skeletal Class II division 1 malocclusion : A case report

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Abstract

Aim and objective of the present case report was to evaluate the management of skeletal Class II division 1 malocclusion in a 13 year old adolescent male patient with extraction of upper 1st and lower 2nd premolars . Clinical and cephalometric evaluation revealed skeletal Class II division 1 malocclusion with severe maxillary incisor proclination, convex profile, increased mandibular plane angle, incompetent lips, 14 mm overjet and deep overbite. After extraction of upper 1st and lower 2nd premolars, canine retraction was done by Class II elastics which was followed by retraction of severely proclined upper anterior teeth by judicious control of third order bend in rectangular stainless steel arch wire with “V” loop. Simultaneous alignment, leveling and correction of deep curve of Spee was done in lower arch. For anchorage management, intraoral anchorage with tip back & toe in bends in stainless steel arch wire was satisfactory. Following treatment marked improvement in patient’s smile, facial profile and lip competence were achieved and there was a remarkable increase in the patient’s confidence and quality of life.

Keywords: Skeletal Class II division1 malocclusion, adolescent patient, Class II elastic, tip back and toe in bend.

Introduction:

Class II division 1 malocclusion is more prevalent than any type of malocclusion after Class I malocclusion in our country.^{1,2} Over the last decade, increasing numbers of adults have become aware of orthodontic treatment and are demanding high quality treatment, in the shortest possible time with increased efficiency and reduced costs.³ Class II malocclusions can be treated by several means, according to the characteristics associated with the problem, such as anteroposterior discrepancy, age, and patient compliance.⁴ Methods include extraoral appliances, functional appliances and fixed appliances associated with Class II intermaxillary elastics.⁵ On the other hand, correction of Class II malocclusions in adolescent patients usually include extraoral orthopaedic appliances with selective removal of permanent teeth. The indications for extractions in orthodontic practice have historically been controversial.⁶⁻⁸ Premolars are probably the most commonly extracted teeth for orthodontic purposes as they are conveniently located between

The anterior and posterior segments. Variations in extraction sequences including upper and lower first or second premolars have been recommended by different authors for a variety of reasons.⁹⁻¹⁴ For correction of Class II malocclusions in adolescent patients, extractions can involve 2 maxillary premolars¹⁵ or 2 maxillary and 2 mandibular premolars.¹⁶ It is usually not the skeletal characteristics of a Class II malocclusion that primarily determine whether it should be treated with 2 or 4 premolar extractions but, rather, the dentoalveolar characteristics.

The extraction of only 2 maxillary premolars is generally indicated when there is no crowding or cephalometric discrepancy in the mandibular arch.^{17,18} Extraction of 4 premolars is indicated primarily for crowding in the mandibular arch, a cephalometric discrepancy, or a combination of both, in growing patients.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ Recent studies have shown that patient satisfaction with camouflage treatment is similar to that achieved with surgical mandibular advancement.²⁰

Case Report

Pretreatment assessment

A 13 year old male reported to the Orthodontic Department at Dhaka Dental College & Hospital with multiple complaints “my teeth stick out”, “I am unable to close my lips” “I feel embarrassed when I laugh”. Extra oral examination revealed a long symmetrical face, convex hard and soft tissue profile, lip trap and an acute nasolabial angle. The patient showed a good range of mandibular movements and no TMJ symptoms. Intra

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oral examination revealed that the patient had a full Class II molar and canine relationship, excessively proclined maxillary incisors with an overjet of 14mm, traumatic deep overbite and severely crowded lower arch. (Fig 1,2) Cephalometric examination revealed Class II skeletal relation with severe maxillary incisor proclination with vertical growth pattern (fig 1,2). Although the underlying sagittal jaw discrepancy was severe, the selective extraction of two 1st premolar teeth in the upper arch and two 2nd premolar teeth in lower arch was considered acceptable. Our treatment objective focused on the chief complaint of the patient, and the treatment plan was individualized based on the specific treatment goals.

Figure 1: Pre treatment study model left & right buccal view

Figure 2. Pre treatment extra oral & intra oral photographs

Diagnosis:

Skeletal Class II division 1 malocclusion with severe maxillary incisor proclination, convex profile, high mandibular plane angle, lip trap, incompetent lips, 14 mm overjet and traumatic deep overbite.

Treatment objectives:

1. Achieve lip competency
2. Develop an ideal overjet and overbite
3. Correct the anteroposterior relationship
4. Achieve occlusal intercuspation with a Class I canine and molar relationship
5. Improve the profile and facial esthetics

Treatment plan:

1. Extraction of maxillary first and mandibular second premolars.
2. Alignment & leveling of upper and lower arches.
3. Correction of deep curve of Spee to reduce deep overbite.
4. Retraction of upper canines by class II elastics.
5. Upper arch contraction and use of intermaxillary elastics.
6. Final settling of the occlusion and arch coordination.

Treatment Progress

The maxillary first and mandibular second premolars were extracted. The first molars were banded and the maxillary and mandibular teeth were bonded from premolar to premolar with a 0.018 x 0.025 standard edgewise brackets. Retractions of upper canines was done in 0.016 inch round stainless steel arch wire with stop loops and tip back and toe-in anchorage bends and use of class II elastics.

Figure 3. After Canine retraction, upper arch contraction with Class II elastics started (right buccal, frontal and left buccal view)

Figure 4. Rectangular (0.017 X 0.025) arch wire with " V " loop for upper arch contraction

Arch contraction and closure of extraction spaces in upper arch was done by rectangular(0.017 X 0.025 inch) Stainless Steel archwire with “V” loops with proper control of third order bend ‘Torque’. (Fig. 3 & 4). Use of Class II elastics provide anchorage loss in the lower arch to establish class I molar relationship and anchorage reinforcement in the upper arch. Final settling of occlusion was done with proper interdigitation, inclination, angulation, ideal overjet and overbite. Debonded and retention was given by upper and lower Hawley’s retainers. Patient was advised to follow up in retention period.

Post treatment assessment: Lip competency and a straight profile were achieved, improving the patient’s facial appearance. A functional occlusion with normal overjet and overbite; class I canine and molar relationship was achieved(Fig.5,6,7,8&9). Duration of the treatment was 21 months. The patient and his parent were very happy with complete satisfaction.

Figure 5. Pre and post treatment lateral Cephalogram Table

Table 1: Cephalometric Analysis

Variables	Reference Measurements	Pre treatment	Post treatment
SNA	82	85	82.5
SNB	80	74.5	77.5
ANB	2	10.5	5
IIA	130	120	130
U1-SN	104	115	108
GoGn to SN	32	36	35

Figure 6. Superimposition of Cephalometric Tracing Pre Treatment (Black) Post Treatment (Blue)

Pretreatment

Post treatment

Figure 7. Pre & post treatment extra oral photographs

Pre treatment Post treatment
 Figure 8: Pre & Post treatment intra oral photographs

Post treatment follow up:

In this case, skeletal correction was achieved by growth modification. This type of case is considered for long term retention & follow up. After 4 years of follow up, patients aesthetic & profile was excellent (Fig 9).

Pre treatment After Debonding After 04 years
 Figure 9: Excellent prognosis after 04 years of follow up

Discussion:

Patient had improved smile and profile after orthodontic treatment. Upper incisors were retracted to achieve normal incisor inclinations, overjet and overbite. Bilateral Class I canine and molar relation was achieved with maximum intercuspation. The case was successfully managed by contemporary orthodontic technique with intra oral anchorage incorporated in archwire except the increased lower anterior facial height.

Conclusion:

Camouflage treatment of severe Class II malocclusion like this case in adolescents is challenging. Extractions of premolars, if undertaken after a thorough diagnosis leads to positive profile changes and an overall satisfactory facial aesthetics. A well chosen individualized treatment plan, undertaken with sound biomechanical principles and appropriate control of orthodontic mechanics to execute the plan is the surest way to achieve predictable results with minimal side effects.

References

1. Hossain MZ et al, Prevalence of malocclusion and treatment facilities at Dhaka Dental College and Hospital. *Journal of Oral Health*, vol: 1, No. 1, 1994
2. Ahmed N et al, Prevalence of malocclusion and its aetiological factors. *Journal of Oral Health*, Vol. 2 No. 2 April 1996
3. Khan RS, Horrocks EN. A study of adult orthodontic patients and their treatment. *Br J Orthod*,18(3):183-194; 1991.
4. Salzmann JA. *Practice of orthodontics*. Philadelphia: J. B. Lippincott Company; p. 701-24;1966.
5. McNamara, J.A.: Components of Class II malocclusion in children 8-10 years of age, *Angle Orthod*, 51:177-202; 1981.
6. Case C S. The question of extraction in orthodontia. *American Journal of Orthodontics*, 50: 660-691; 1964.
7. Case C S. The extraction debate of 1911 by Case, Dewey, and Cryer. Discussion of Case: the question of extraction in orthodontia. *American Journal of Orthodontics*, 50: 900-912; 1964.
8. Tweed C. Indications for the extraction of teeth in orthodontic procedure. *American Journal of Orthodontics* 30: 405-428; 1944.
9. Stagers J A. A comparison of results of second molar and first premolar extraction treatment. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*, 98: 430-36; 1990.
10. Luecke P E, Johnston L E. The effect of maxillary first premolar extraction and incisor retraction on mandibular position: testing the central dogma of 'functional orthodontics'. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*, 101: 4-12; 1992.
11. Proffit W R, Phillips C, Douvartzidis N. A comparison of outcomes of orthodontic and surgical-orthodontic treatment of Class II malocclusion in adults. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*, 101: 556-565; 1992.
12. Paquette D E, Beattie J R, Johnston L E. A long-term comparison of non extraction and premolar extraction edgewise therapy in 'borderline' Class II patients. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*, 102:1-14; 1992.
13. Taner-Sar soy L, Darendeliler N. The influence of extraction treatment on craniofacial structures: evaluation according to two different factors. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics* 115: 508-514; 1999.
14. Basciftci F A, Usumez S. Effects of extraction and non extraction treatment on Class I and Class II subjects, *Angle Orthodontist* 73: 36-42; 2003.
15. Cleall JF, Begole EA. Diagnosis and treatment of Class II Division 2 malocclusion. *Angle Orthod* 52:38-60; 1982.
16. Strang RHW. *Tratado de ortodoncia*. Buenos Aires: Editorial Bibliografica Argentina; 1957. p. 560-70, 657-71.
17. Bishara SE, Cummins DM, Jakobsen JR, Zaher AR. Dentofacial and soft tissue changes in Class II, Division 1 cases treated with and without extractions. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop* 107:28-37; 1995.
18. Rock WP. Treatment of Class II malocclusions with removable appliances. Part 4. Class II Division 2 treatment. *Br Dent J* 168:298-302; 1990.
19. Arvystas MG. Nonextraction treatment of Class II, Division 1 malocclusions. *Am J Orthod* 88:380-95; 1985.
20. Mihalik, C.A.; Proffit, W.R.; and Phillips, C.: Long-term followup of Class II adults treated with orthodontic camouflage: A comparison with orthognathic surgery outcomes, *Am. J. Orthod.* 123:266-278, 2003.

Dental Technique Improve Smile and Confidence “A Case Report of Post-Traumatic Discolored Teeth-30 Month Follow Up”

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Abstract:

Traumatic injury is very common incident in our mechanical life, which require immediate initial treatment in our regular dental practice. Sudden impact involving the head or face may result in trauma to the teeth and supporting structure¹. This type of problem can be managed by various modern dental procedures considering the general and physical condition of the patient, professional status and economic condition of the patient.

Key words: Discolored broken matured permanent teeth, non-vitality, apical radiolucency, full veneer crown.

Introduction:

- The most frequent causes of traumatic injury are falling while running followed by traffic accident, act of violence and sports² and especially in the rural area due to tube well injury in our country.
- The exposure of the pulp in complicated crown fracture requires more elaborate dental procedure. The initial reaction is haemorrhage at the site of pulp wound. Next a Superficial inflammatory response occurs followed by either a destructive (necrotic) or proliferative (pulp polyp) reaction.³ So the diagnosis of crown fracture with pulp involvement can be made by clinical, radiological and histological examination.

Case report:

A twenty four years old patient with depressed appearance named Md. Jafor came to the department of conservative dentistry and endodontics at BSMMU on 25th November 2007. He had a history of traumatic injury of anterior teeth four years back. Four months back he took his first treatment management in a private

clinic but he was not satisfied of that treatment and was referred by that doctor to come this hospital for better treatment. On clinical and radiological examination I found broken incisal maxillary teeth with severe discoloration and apical radiolucency. Two stages of treatment procedure had been taken. Firstly preservation of teeth by non-surgical endodontic management & Secondly, restoration of teeth with full veneer crown.

Clinical procedure:

An endodontic access cavity was already prepared because of his first treatment management. I removed necrotic debris from the canal and irrigation was done with normal saline. A working length determination x-ray was taken. The canal was prepared up to the file no-80. The canal was attempted to dry but I couldn't make the canal dry. The access was closed with zinc oxide eugenol cement. A second appointment was given after three days later. On second visit the canal was reopened and it was not possible to dry. So a dressing with calcium hydroxide paste was given and closed with zinc oxide eugenol cement. A third appointment was given 7 days later. On third visit it was not possible to dry the canal and again a dressing with calcium hydroxide paste was given. And fourth appointment was given 7 days later. On fourth visit it was possible to dry the canal and the canal was Obturated by lateral condensation technique with gutta-percha point and zinc oxide eugenol sealer. A radiograph was taken and patient was advised to attend for follow up one month later. One month later the patient was examined clinically and there was no pain and tenderness on percussion. On radiological examination the apical radiolucency was slightly less. At this stage the patient was advised to

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restore his teeth with full veneer crown.

Second stage of treatment:

On first visit the teeth were prepared for full veneer crown and impression was taken. On second visit metal trial was given and there was no marginal shortage and retention was good. On third visit porcelain trial was given and trimmed it to make it perfect and attractive appearance. On fourth visit full veneer crown was fitted and patient was very satisfied and patient was advised to come for regular follow up. Thirty month later follow up was taken and patient was completely alright both clinically and radiologically.

Discussion:

Management of discolored teeth especially endodontically treated teeth can be done by bleaching technique but this technique is indicated in case of discoloration of pulp chamber, dentine discoloration and is not indicated in superficial enamel discoloration, severe dentin loss, discolored composite etc.⁶ A

successful outcome depends mainly on the etiology, correct diagnosis and proper selection of bleaching technique.⁴ Tooth whitening is fast and affordable way to revitalized smile but it can be dizzying trying to decide which system is right for particular case. Extreme make over revealed how porcelain veneer could make dramatic smile changes.⁵

Conclusion:

Cosmetic dentistry is a hot topic now. The main objective of this treatment procedure is to preserve the permanent teeth and restoration with full veneer crown, which return the natural appearance of the patient and leading his life with great confidence.

Reference:

1. Ingle: Backland. Endodontics, 5th edition, Endodontic consideration of Dental Trauma.
2. Ingle: Backland. Endodontics, 5th edition, Endodontic consideration of Dental Trauma.
3. Ingle: Backland. Endodontics, 5th edition, Endodontic consideration of Dental Trauma.
4. Ingle: Backland. Endodontics, 5th edition, tooth discoloration and Bleaching
5. Dentistry.Com-article for category: tooth whitening
6. Ingle: Backland. Endodontics, 5th edition, tooth discoloration and Bleaching

Pattern and Distribution of Jaw fracture: A study conducted on 422 patients of jaw fracture

AFMS Rahman¹, T Begum², M Hasan³, M Ahmed⁴

Introduction

The maxillofacial region may frequently uphold trauma due to various factors such as road traffic accident (RTA), political violence, assault, fall, industrial injury and sports injury. In western countries assaults are replacing the RTA as the commonest etiological factors^{1,2}. However in developing countries like Bangladesh, RTA remains the commonest causes of maxillofacial trauma^{3,4,5,6,7}. It is due to overcrowding, insecure road, violation of traffic rules and unskilled driving⁸. In case of Mandible fracture prevalence is the most in the body of the mandible, it is 30-40%, and then comes angle (25-31%), condyle (15-17%), symphysis (7-15%), ramus, alveolar and coronoid process. In case of midfacial fracture the prevalence is more in zygomatico maxillary complex (40%), then Le-Forte I, II, III (35%), zygomatic arch (10%), alveolar process of maxilla (5%), smash fracture (5%), and other (5%).⁹

In Bangladesh Molla MR reported that the major causes of mandible fracture was road traffic accident (58.4%), the other causes were falls (13.6%), work related (12.8%), sports related (4.8%), assault (0.8%) and pathological fracture (1.6%)⁶.

Treatment of jaw fractures has changed over the last 20 years. There has been a decrease in the use of wire osteosynthesis and intermaxillary fixation and an increase in preference for open reduction and internal

fixation with miniplates. This has helped to reduce malocclusion, non-union, improved mouth opening, speech, oral hygiene, decrease loss and the ability for patients to return to work earlier.

The aim of the study was to examine the pattern and treatment of mandibular fractures.

This was a Prospective cross-sectional study in the period of January 2007 to June 2008 at the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial surgery Dhaka Dental College Hospital.

Study population: Patients attended to out patient department of DDCH with jaw bone fracture irrespective of age and sex.

Sample size: 422 patients with jaw bone fracture.

Assignment of procedure: Among all patients admitted to hospital with facial bone fracture, study subjects were assigned recording the data including the history sheet.

Results

This was a prospective cross sectional study conducted in the outpatient department of oral and maxillofacial surgery of Dhaka Dental College from January 2007 to June 2008 presenting with jaw fracture. The main objective of the study was to assess proportion of jaw fractures among the admitted patients.

Table 1: Distribution of attendant's patients in the OMS outpatient department

sex	Hospital attendants		%
	Total Jaw fracture		
Male	2494	304	12.19
female	2223	118	5.31
Total	4717	422	8.94

Table 1 shows the number of patients attendant in the OMS OPD during January 2007 to June 2008. Total 4717 were attended in the OPD and among them 8.94 % had jaw fractures.

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Table 2 : Age distribution of study population

age	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative percent
0-12	61	14.45	14.45
13-20	46	10.9	25.35
21-30	154	36.49	61.84
31-40	77	18.25	80.09
41-50	52	12.32	92.41
51-60	21	4.97	97.38
60>	11	2.62	100.00
Total	422	100.00	

FIGURE 1: Shows distribution of age group of the study subject (n=82) , 0-12years were 15%, 13-20 years were 37%, 21-30 years were 37%, 31-40 years were 18%, 41-50 years were 12%, 51- 60 years were 5% and 61-70 years were only 2% of the total respondents.

Table 3: Distribution of cause of jaw fracture:

Cause	Frequency	Percent
RTA	257	60.9
Assault	67	15.9
Fall	46	10.9
Sports	31	7.3
Others	21	5.0

Table 3 shows distribution of cause of jaw fracture: 60.9% due to RTA followed by assault were 15.9%.

Table 4: Distribution of pattern of jaw fracture:

Site	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative percent
Mandible alone	227	53.8	53.8
Maxilla alone	92	21.8	75.6
Mand+ Maxilla	57	13.5	89.1
Mand+ Zygoma	10	2.4	91.5
Max +Zygoma	36	8.5	100.0
Total	422	100.0	

Table 4 shows only mandible fracture occurred in 53.8% (n=227) of total study subjects and maxilla alone in 21.8%, both mandible and maxilla were 13.5%, maxilla with zygomatic were 8.5% and the lowest 2.4% found in mandible with zygomatic bone fracture

TABLE 5: Age distribution of the indoor admitted patient

Age group	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0-12	12	14.6	14.6	14.6
13-20	9	11.0	11.0	25.6
21-30	30	36.6	36.6	62.2
31-40	15	18.3	18.3	80.5
41-50	10	12.2	12.2	92.7
51-60	4	4.9	4.9	97.6
61-70	2	2.4	2.4	100.0
Total	82	100.0	100.0	

Table 5 : Shows distribution of age group of the study subject (n=82) , 0-12years were 15%, 13-20 years were 37%, 21-30 years were 37%, 31-40 years were 18%, 41- 50 years were 12%, 51- 60 years were 5% and 61-70 years were only 2% of the total respondents.

Table 8: Distribution of site of mandibular fractures:

Site	Number	Percent
Body	91	31
Angle	42	27.9
Condyle	41	13.9
Parasymphysis	57	19.4
Symphysis	21	7.1
Dentoalveolar	02	0.7
Total	294	100.0

Table 8 shows mandible fracture has specific pattern of distribution. Almost one third of the study subjects attended with fracture at body of mandible (31%), 27.9% had fracture at the angle of mandible, fracture at parasymphysis, condyle and symphysis were found to be 19.4%, 13.9% and 7.1% respectively.

Table 9: Pattern of treatment of Jaw fracture (out patient dept):

Type	Number	Percent
close reduction with arch bar wiring	210	49.8
open reduction (intraoral approach) and miniplate fixation	80	18.9
Admission for major surgery(by general anaesthesia)	82	19.4
Missing	50	11.8
Total	422	100.0

Table 9 shows in out patient department almost half of patients received close reduction with arch bar wiring.

Figure 9: Pattern of Treatment of jaw fractures (indoor patient)

DISCUSSION

Bangladesh is a developing country with 150 million people and its road traffic system is very poor. Thus the prevalence of maxillofacial trauma fracture significantly high due to road traffic accident which often affect the mandible of the facial bone. Epidemiological survey for jaw fracture in Bangladesh though not yet been done but several cross sectional study on jaw fractures have been done.

Current study investigated the pattern, causes and management of maxillofacial fractures along with the common complications in maxillofacial trauma. Current study was conducted among 422 maxillofacial fracture patients attending in out patient department of Dhaka Dental College Hospital and also management with common complications of jaw fractures among 82 admitted patients underwent open reduction with miniplate fixation.

Regarding age distribution it was found that highest percentage (36.49%) of patients were in the age ranges of 21-30 years followed by in the age group of 31-40 years (18.25%).

The finding is almost similar in several of the multi-centered study although Prevalence of injury among young age group was found rather higher in the current series,¹⁰ Facial trauma patient were mostly (68.6%) male. High mobility of male might be the reason for higher prevalence of trauma among males. The finding accords with most of the findings of the studies where sex was considered as variable¹¹

In several studies results showed that the greatest number of maxillo-mandibular fractures occurred in patients between the age group 21-30 years, with a male to female ratio of 3:1. Assault was found to have been the leading aetiological factor (29.9%) followed by motor vehicle and motor cycle accidents (27.3%), falls (18.2%), bar fights (9.1%), sports (8.6%), spouse abuse (3.7%) and work injuries constituted 3.2%. Mandibular fractures out-numbered maxillary fractures in a ratio of 4:1. Of the mandibular fractures, fracture of the body of

the mandible occurred most followed by fracture at the angle of the mandible, symphysis, condyle, alveolar and ramus.¹²

In this study, jaw fracture has specific pattern of distribution. Almost half of the Subjects admitted with fracture of mandible (53.8%) and 21.8% had fracture of the maxilla alone. Fracture of both mandible and maxilla, mandible and zygomatic, maxilla and zygomatic were found to be 13.5%, 2.4 % and 8.5% respectively.

In the current study occlusion has been evaluated as satisfactory occlusion and mal occlusion. Occlusion has been the key variable for measuring the outcome and comparison of treatment modalities. Five of the components, Molar relation, Canine relation, anterior open bite, posterior open bite and cross bite were taken in to account for assessing the occlusion as the out come of treatment.

Almost all methods were used for fixation by miniplate but simple methods of reduction and immobilization were used on our patient basis under local anesthesia. The results were satisfactory.

Conclusion & Recommendations

In the present study, the mandibular fractures were more prevalent in male patients and during the 3rd decade of life. The most common cause was RTA and the more frequently affected regions were body and condyle. Isolated mandibular fracture occur in more than 50 percent of cases. Most patients were treated with close reduction and conventional means.

It is hoped that assessments such as the one presented here will be valuable to the government agencies and health care professionals involved in planning futures programmed of prevention and treatment.

References:

1. Vincent Townend, JRI, Langdon JD, Sepherd JR. The epidemiology of maxillofacial trauma. Appendix in William(ED), maxillofacial injuries. Edinburgh, Churchill Livingstone.1985: 1053-1063.
2. Cohen LE, Felson M. Social change and crime rate trends: a routine activity approach. American Sociological Review 1979; 44: 588-608.
3. Tanaka N, Tomitsuka, Shionoya K. Etiology of maxillofacial fractures. British Journal of Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery. 1994; 32: 19-23.
4. Nair KB, Paul G. Incidence and etiology of fractures of the facio-maxillary skeleton in Trivandrum: a retrospective study, British Journal of Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery.1986; 24:40-44.

5. Thomas DW, Sageman M, Shepherd JP. Trends in the management of fractured mandibles *Health Trends*. 1995; 26:113.
6. Molla MR. Prevalence of mandibular fracture in Bangladesh: an analysis with 125 cases. *Journal of Bangladesh Dental Society*, 1989; 5:10-13.
7. Molla MR. Prevalence of jaw fractures in road traffic accident in Bangladesh: an analysis with 98 cases. *Journal of Bangladesh Dental Society*, 1994;10: 40-44.
8. Bhuiyan RA. Management of maxillofacial trauma in Bangladesh: International seminar on Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, 3rd to 5th Sept 2004, Dhaka, Bangladesh
9. Neelima AM: Text book of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, 1st ed. Japee, India. 2002: 302-303.
10. Shah A, Shah AA, Salam A. Pattern and management of mandibular fractures: a study conducted on 264 patients. *Pakistan Oral and Dental Journal*, 2006: Vol 27, No 1, pp 103-106
11. Tanaka N, Tomitsuka K, Shionoya K, Andou H, Kimijima Y, Tashiro T, Amagasa T. *Br J Oral Maxillofac Surg*. 1994 Feb;32(1):pp19-23.
12. Moshy J, Mosha HJ, Lema PA. Prevalence of maxillo-mandibular fractures in mainland Tanzania. *East Afr Med J*. 1996 Mar;73(3):172-5.

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